

Reply Slip

Please complete and return this form only if you do NOT wish to join the SAFER Wearables Study

Title: The SAFER Wearables Study:
A study of the acceptability and performance of wearables for atrial fibrillation screening in older adults.

Chief Investigator: Dr Peter Charlton, University of Cambridge

IRAS Project ID: 283812 {Invite ID: XXXX}

If you are willing, please indicate why you do not wish to take part:
(tick as many as apply)

- I don't want to take part in another research study
- I don't want to wear the devices
- I don't have time
- I have a pacemaker

- Other reasons:
